

2014

ISSN 2278-5655

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly)

Peer-Reviewed Journal

Impact factor:0.948

Aug-Sep Issues

Chief-Editor

Ubale Amol Baban

PEER-REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near
TV Towar,Badlapur, MSief

**EFFECT OF SMART CLASS TEACHING ON THE ACHIEVEMENT OF 8TH CLASS
STUDENTS IN SOCIAL STUDIES**

Education

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Abstract

The 21st century is well known for the use of technology in all the fields like business, engineering, medical, transportation and education. Present research study aimed to compare the effectiveness of teaching through lecture method and smart class method on the Achievement in Social Studies of 8th Standard Students. For this study experimental research method was used to study the effectiveness of smart class teaching. Results of this study clearly indicate that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students in post-test of controlled group and experimental group of subject social Studies.

Introduction

Teaching large lecture classes can present problems for even the most experienced faculty members. It can be difficult to keep students' attention and elicit questions, responses, or other forms of interaction with the lecture material and the instructor. Passive learning occurs when students use their senses to take in information from a lecture, reading assignment, or audiovisual. Traditional lecture is not an effective learning environment for many of our students

because so many students do not participate actively during a traditional lecture. Technology makes the teaching-learning process very easy and interesting. Now, technology is making life easier for both students and educators. Many researchers reported their studies on the integration of technology in the process of teaching and learning as efforts to amplify students' performance, teaching effectiveness, as well as teachers' productivity (Wang et al., 2008). In an earlier study it was also found that integrating technology is more than just helping people to use computers, but it is also for helping teachers to utilize it for learning. In fact, technology should make teaching and learning process easier and get along with it. Thus, technology integration in classrooms takes more than just having the facilities installed in schools; much consideration is needed to find the right way of how it can be utilized for education.

Nowadays, teaching is becoming one of the most challenging professions in India where knowledge is expanding rapidly and much of it is available to students as well teachers at any time and anywhere. To make education more interesting and learning a fun experience many schools are depending on information and technology enabled smart class rooms. A lot of interest has been expressed among educationalists towards the key factors that enable technological implementation in schools (Handler, 1993; Collis, 1996; Davis, 1997; Haughey and Anderson, 1998; Burge and Roberts, 1998; Somekh, 1998). The black boards in the class rooms are replaced by digital black boards. The audio-visual rooms and interactive sessions replaced the traditional textbook and notebook depended study. With the use of latest technologies, the tech-savvy students started enjoying studies and keenly participate in the learning process. Smart boards and audio visual rooms are adding a new dimension to the teaching style. With the introduction of smart class rooms learning process become more lively and interactive. Earlier in geographic classes explaining about a place was restricted to showing the place in the text book and explaining about it. Now with the help of internet a teacher can show in the Google Map where exactly the place is located and details about the people, culture and traditions. Rather than just hearing lectures such interactive classes helps students to know more about a subject. Smart Class was conceived and developed around the ideology that for

technology to become an integral part of day to day teaching and learning practices in schools, it needs to move right in to the classroom where students and teachers spend over 80% of their teaching learning time. Smartclass also enables teachers to quickly assess how much of a particular lesson students have been able to assimilate during the class. Once a topic is covered, the teacher gives the class a set of questions on a large screen.

The word is dynamic in nature. In this age of competition students have a desire to achieve more and more academically. In most of the schools only lecture method have been used for all the teaching of different subjects and some students like to read only prescribe books at the time of their examinations to get only passing marks but result in both the cases are similar. So the investigator is keenly interested in finding the effect of smart class teaching on the achievement of students in Social Studies.

Objectives of the Research Study

1. To compare the effectiveness of teaching through lecture method and smart class method in relation to student's achievement studying at secondary level in Social Studies.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the scores of students in post test of controlled and experimental group after teaching through lecture and smart class method.

Research Methodology

For present research study, experimental research method was used to study the effectiveness of teaching through lecture method and smart class method.

Sample

By using random sampling method 70 students of 8th standard was selected from a government aided school of Sonipat city, Haryana state, as a sample. On the basis of academic performance two equivalent groups were made, out of which one was controlled group and other was experimental group. Each group comprises 35 students.

Tools used for present Research Study

Teacher made achievement test was used as a tool for present research study. The test is of 35 marks and comprising of 35 objective type questions.

Procedure of the Present Research Study

The experimental group was treated with smart class teaching and controlled group was with lecture method. Observation was made to determine as to what difference appears in achievements in the experimental group and controlled group.

The Designs of this research study is as follows-

Statistical Techniques Used

The following statistical techniques were used in the study

1. Mean
2. Standard Deviations
3. t-test to compare the groups

Result and discussion

Hypothesis-: There is no significant difference between the scores of students in post test of controlled and experimental group after teaching through lecture and smart class method.

Table-1: Table showing the mean scores of students in post-test of Controlled and Experimental group of subject Social Studies.

Groups (Students)	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of Significance
Controlled Group	35	20	6.30	4.09	Significant
Experimental Group	35	25	3.68		

The calculated t-value is 4.09 which is greater than the table t-value at both of the level of significance (0.05 and 0.01), hence it is significant. Therefore the hypothesis- There is no significant difference between the scores of students in post test of controlled and experimental group after teaching through lecture and smart class method, is rejected.

Hence it was inferred that there is significant difference in the achievement of students in post-test of controlled group and experimental group.

Conclusion

The present investigation shows that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students in post-test of controlled group and experimental group of 8th class in Social Studies. Hence, it is clearly shown that the use of smart class equipment for teaching Social Studies of 8th class is a influencing factor in the academic achievement of the students. Students secure more when they are taught through smart class teaching.

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